

Nonholonomic Motion Planning using Stokes's Theorem

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Abstract

Nonholonomic mechanical systems are governed by constraints of motion that are nonintegrable differential expressions. Unlike holonomic constraints, these differential constraints do not reduce the number of dimensions of the configuration space of a system. Therefore a nonholonomic system can access a configuration space of dimension higher than the number of the degrees of freedom of the system. In this paper, we develop an algorithm for planning admissible trajectories for nonholonomic systems that will take the system from one point in its configuration space to another. In our algorithm, we first converge the independent variables to their desired values and then use closed trajectories of the independent variables to converge the dependent variables. We use Stokes's theorem in our algorithm to convert the problem of finding a closed path into that of finding a surface area in the space of the independent variables such that the dependent variables converge to their desired values as the independent variables traverse along the boundary of this surface area. The salient features of our algorithm is apparent in the example of a disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface.

1 Introduction

Nonholonomic mechanical systems are governed by nonintegrable differential constraints of the form

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji} dq_i + a_{jt} dt = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (1)$$

where, the q 's represent the generalized coordinates, t represents time, and the a 's are, in general functions of the q 's and t . As a result of the nonintegrable nature of these differential constraints, it is not possible to obtain functions of the form

$$\phi_j(q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n, t) = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

that will enable us to eliminate some of the dependent variables. Naturally, nonholonomic systems require more coordinates for their description than there are degrees of freedom in the system.

An interesting feature of nonholonomic mechanical systems is their ability to access a configuration space

of higher dimension than the number of its degrees of freedom. A simple example is that of a disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface. The configuration space of the disk rolling on the x - y plane, shown in Fig.1, is described by the four coordinates (x, y, θ, α) , but the system has only two degrees of freedom because of the following two nonholonomic constraints

$$\begin{aligned} dx - r \sin \alpha d\theta &= 0 \\ dy - r \cos \alpha d\theta &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In spite of having only two degrees of freedom, it is quite intuitive that the rolling disk can arrive at any configuration (x, y, θ, α) from any other through proper path planning. Such a property is common to nonholonomic mechanical systems and can be attributed to the nonintegrable nature of their differential constraints.

Figure 1. A disk rolling on a flat surface is described by four configuration variables: x , y , θ , and α . The disk has however two degrees of freedom due to the presence of two nonholonomic constraints.

For the rolling disk, our intuition can be strengthened if we consider the following example. Suppose, it is desired that the disk in Fig.1 change its coordinates from (x, y, θ, α) to $(x_d, y_d, \theta, \alpha)$. Then a feasible trajectory would be the path segments AO and OC . The disk would roll forward from A to O , and then roll backward from O to C . The individual path segments AO and OC should have equal lengths such that θ comes back to its initial value at the end of the path. Furthermore, the straight lines AB and CD should be tangent to the path segments AO and OC respectively, at the points A and C . This will ensure that the net change of the variable α will also be zero over the complete path. Such a path can always be planned and this leads us to believe that the dependent variables x and y can indeed be changed arbitrarily through cyclic motion of the independent variables θ and α . Therefore to converge all the configuration variables of the disk from one set of values to another, we could first converge the independent variables from their initial values to their desired values without being concerned about the evolution of the dependent variables, and then use cyclic motion of the independent variables to converge the dependent variables to their desired values.

The majority of the researchers have used differential geometric tools for nonholonomic motion planning [3], [6], [7], [8], [9]. The multibody car system was studied in [6] and it was concluded from the Lie algebra that it is a well controllable system. Based on similar analyses a solution to the rolling disk, the front wheel drive car and the car with a single trailer was provided in [7]. An elegant method for steering a general class of nonholonomic systems using sinusoids was proposed in [3]. In this algorithm, the independent variables were first steered to their desired configuration ignoring the evolution of the dependent variables. The dependent variables were subsequently converged to their desired values using closed trajectories of the independent variables. Such an approach was proposed earlier [5], for the motion planning of a space manipulator, where the cyclic motion of the joints of the space manipulator was used to change the orientation of the whole system.

In this paper, we will discuss the motion planning of nonholonomic systems using an algorithm in which the goal is to find a closed trajectory of the independent variables that converge the dependent variables to their desired values. In our approach, we use Stokes's theorem to reduce this problem into finding a surface area such that the dependent variables converge to their desired values while the independent variables travel along the boundary of this surface area. The main advantage is the global nature of our planning algorithm, unlike the local path planning approach based on Lyapunov functions [4]. Due to the global nature of the algorithm, questions pertaining to the reachability of the system can be readily answered, problems related to singularity can be tackled, and feasible trajectories can be easily planned even in the presence of additional constraints. For a nonholonomic system like a space robot, these additional constraints may appear in the form of joint limits or ob-

stacles in the workspace. Our algorithm additionally provides us with insight into trajectories that produce repeatable motion. Repeatability in the motion may simply be a desirable property, as in the case of space robots, or may even be used for singularity avoidance as in the case of a rolling disk.

This paper is organized as follows. In section 2 we discuss the mathematical preliminaries and the properties of nonholonomic systems. In section 3, we present our algorithm for the nonholonomic motion planning through the example of a disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface.

2 Mathematical preliminaries

2.1 Line and surface integrals

Stokes's Theorem [2] Let S be a piecewise smooth oriented surface in space and let the boundary of S be a piecewise smooth closed curve C . Let $\vec{v}(x, y, z)$ be a continuous vector function which has continuous first partial derivatives in a domain in space which contains S . Then

$$\oint_C (v_1 dx + v_2 dy + v_3 dz) = \iint_S \left[\left(\frac{\partial v_3}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial z} \right) \cos \alpha + \left(\frac{\partial v_1}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial x} \right) \cos \beta + \left(\frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \right) \cos \gamma \right] dA \quad (4)$$

where, the positive direction along C is then defined as the direction along which an observer, traveling on the positive side of S , would proceed in keeping the enclosed area to his left. α , β , and γ are the direction cosines of the normal to the surface S .

If we restrict ourselves to the x - y plane, then Stokes's theorem simplifies to the form

$$\iint_S \left(\frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \right) dx dy = \oint_C (v_1 dx + v_2 dy) \quad (5)$$

which is essentially a statement of Green's theorem [2]. Another theorem that will serve as an important tool for our analysis deals with the path independence of line integrals. This theorem is formally stated next [2]

Theorem 2 Let $\vec{v} = v_1 \vec{i} + v_2 \vec{j} + v_3 \vec{k}$, and let v_1 , v_2 , and v_3 be continuous functions of x , y , and z in a domain D of space. Then the line integral

$$\int_C (v_1 dx + v_2 dy + v_3 dz) \quad (6)$$

is independent of path if and only if the differential form under the integral sign is exact in D , or equivalently the integral is zero for every simple closed path in D , or equivalently $\nabla \times \vec{v} = 0$, everywhere in D .

From the above theorem we see that the necessary and sufficient condition for the exactness of the differential form under the integral sign in Eq.(6) is

$$\frac{\partial v_2}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial z}, \quad \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x} \quad (7)$$

2.2 Properties of nonholonomic systems

In this section we discuss some of the important properties of nonholonomic systems. In section 3 we will use these properties to develop our motion planning scheme.

In section 1 we mentioned that nonholonomic constraints are expressions of the form as in Eq.(1) that cannot be simplified into expressions of the form as in Eq.(2). To further our discussion, we consider again the example of the disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface whose first constraint equation is

$$dx - r \sin \alpha d\theta = 0 \quad (8)$$

The above constraint is not an exact differential since there exists no function $\phi(x, \alpha, \theta)$ such that Eq.(8) can be reduced to the form

$$d\phi = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \alpha} d\alpha + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} d\theta = 0$$

Furthermore, Eq.(8) cannot be multiplied by an integrating factor to yield an exact differential. Hence it is not integrable. It can be shown that the necessary and sufficient condition for the integrability of the differential constraint in n variables [1]

$$v_1 dx_1 + v_2 dx_2 + \dots + v_n dx_n = 0$$

is that the set of equations

$$v_\nu \left(\frac{\partial v_\mu}{\partial x_\lambda} - \frac{\partial v_\lambda}{\partial x_\mu} \right) + v_\mu \left(\frac{\partial v_\lambda}{\partial x_\nu} - \frac{\partial v_\nu}{\partial x_\lambda} \right) + v_\lambda \left(\frac{\partial v_\nu}{\partial x_\mu} - \frac{\partial v_\mu}{\partial x_\nu} \right) = 0, \quad (\lambda, \mu, \nu = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (9)$$

are satisfied simultaneously, and identically. Applying this criterion to Eq.(8) we confirm that the expression is not integrable.

The discussion in this section so far enables us to ascertain the nonholonomy of a dynamical system from its differential constraints. We now investigate the manifestation of these nonholonomic constraints.

If a dynamical system is described by n generalized coordinates and m holonomic constraints of the form as in Eq.(2), the motion of the system is always confined to a manifold or surface of dimension $(n - m)$, which is equal to the number of degrees of freedom of the system. Then, if we specify the $(n - m)$ independent variables, it is possible to uniquely determine the remaining m dependent variables. This is not true when the constraints are nonholonomic or nonintegrable expressions of the form as in Eq.(1). The kinematic effect of a nonholonomic constraint is to constrain the direction of the allowable motions at any given point in the configuration space. But this does not reduce the number of dimensions in the

configuration space, nor does it limit the variety of configurations available to the system. As a direct consequence, given the values of the independent variables, it is not possible to uniquely specify the values of the dependent variables of a nonholonomic system. When the independent variables take one set of values from another, the change in the dependent variables depend upon the path taken by the independent variables. Quite naturally, if the independent variables travel along a closed path, the values of the dependent variables at the beginning and end of the path are usually not the same.

The above mentioned property of a nonholonomic system is better understood by the use of Theorem 2 on line integrals. Comparing Eq.(7) (conditions for exactness) to Eq.(9) (conditions for integrability), or directly from the definition of integrability, we know that exactness implies integrability. Therefore it follows that a nonintegrable expression is not exact. Consider now a nonholonomic system with one dependent variable p which is constrained by the differential expression $dp = v_1 dx + v_2 dy + v_3 dz$, where $x, y,$ and z are the independent variables. $v_1, v_2,$ and v_3 are continuous functions of $x, y,$ and z . Since the system is nonholonomic or nonintegrable, the differential form $v_1 dx + v_2 dy + v_3 dz$ is not exact. Therefore it follows from Theorem 2 that the change of p is path dependent, and this change is not zero for every closed path. This suggests the following:

- It is possible to change the coordinates of the dependent variable p of the nonholonomic system using appropriate closed trajectories of the independent variables.

On the basis of the above statement discussed above, we now assume that there exists some closed trajectory C of the independent variables $x, y,$ and z that produce a change in the dependent variable p by some desired amount Δp . If (x_0, y_0, z_0) be any point on this closed trajectory and if (x_0, y_0, z_0, p_0) be the initial configuration of the system, then after the system moves along C once, its configuration will be $(x_0, y_0, z_0, p_0 + \Delta p)$ (refer to Fig.2 (a)). If the closed curve C was traversed in the opposite direction, then the final configuration of the system would have been $(x_0, y_0, z_0, p_0 - \Delta p)$. Now consider the initial configuration of the system to be (x', y', z', p_0) , such that (x', y', z') does not lie on C . Let P be any path segment connecting the point (x', y', z') and any point (x_0, y_0, z_0) on the closed curve C . Let δp denote the change in the dependent variable p , as $x, y,$ and z move along the path segment P from (x', y', z') to (x_0, y_0, z_0) . Then, if the system moves from the initial configuration (x', y', z', p_0) to the closed curve C along P , then moves once along the closed curve C , and finally retraces the path P backwards, the configuration of the system at the end of the path (see Fig.2 (b)) will be $(x', y', z', p_0 + \Delta p)$. This is true because the surface integral of the area bounded by the closed curve beginning and ending at the point (x', y', z') is equal to the surface integral of the area bounded by the closed curve C . From this discussion it follows that

the closed curve C that can bring about the desired change in the dependent variable can lie anywhere in the space defined by the independent generalized coordinates - it does not have to pass through the initial configuration of the system. Of course, it would be simpler to plan a closed path passing through the initial configuration of the system, but such a path may not be feasible due to singularity problems. We will discuss the singularity problem, in the situation of a rolling disk, in section 3.

Figure 2 (a) The closed trajectory C in the independent variables x , y , and z produces a change in the dependent variable p by an amount Δp . The initial configuration of the system - (1), lies on this closed trajectory.

3 Nonholonomic motion planning using Stokes's theorem

We revisit the classical example of the disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface. The configuration space of the rolling disk, as discussed in section 1, is described by (x, y, θ, α) . The independent variables of the system are θ and α , and x and y are the dependent variables constrained by the expressions given in Eq.(3). While planning a path from an initial configuration of the disk $(x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i)$ to some desired configuration $(x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f)$, we first converge the independent variables to their desired values using some simple trajectory without concern for the evolution of the dependent variables. This trajectory may however be important in order to avoid a singularity problem, which we shall discuss soon. At the end of this trajectory (path segment OP in Fig.3), the dependent variables are assumed to drift to values x_d and y_d . Now the task is to plan a closed path for the independent variables θ and α such that the dependent variables x and y change their values from x_d and y_d to x_f and y_f respectively. Let C be such a closed path in the θ - α plane. Then the change of the variables x and y are

represented as

$$(x_f - x_d) = \oint_C r \sin \alpha d\theta = \iint_S -r \cos \alpha d\theta d\alpha \quad (10)$$

$$(y_f - y_d) = \oint_C r \cos \alpha d\theta = \iint_S r \sin \alpha d\theta d\alpha \quad (11)$$

Figure 2 (b) The closed trajectory C in the independent variables x , y , and z produces a change in the dependent variable p by an amount Δp . The initial configuration of the system - (1), does not lie on this closed trajectory.

where, we applied Green's theorem, given by Eq.(5), to convert the line integral into the surface integral. Therefore, S is the surface in the θ - α plane within the closed curve C . We choose the closed curve C as the directed rectangular path $PQRS$ shown in Fig.3. For this rectangular path, Eqs.(10) and (11) yield

$$(x_f - x_d) = -2ar \sin(b/2) \cos(\alpha_f + b/2) \quad (12)$$

$$(y_f - y_d) = 2ar \sin(b/2) \sin(\alpha_f + b/2) \quad (13)$$

Assuming $b \neq 2n\pi$, $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$, we solve for a and b as follows

$$b = 2[-\alpha_f + \arctan 2(y_f - y_d, x_d - x_f)], 0 < b < 4\pi \quad (14)$$

$$a = \frac{\{(x_f - x_d)^2 + (y_f - y_d)^2\}^{1/2}}{2r \sin(b/2)} \quad (15)$$

Since the solutions to the arctan 2 function differ by an angle of 2π , b in Eq.(14) can always be chosen to be a positive number with an upper limit of 4π . Furthermore, Eq.(14) was derived from Eqs.(12) and (13) with the assumption that $a \sin(b/2)$ is a positive number. Therefore in Eq.(15) we always choose the positive square root of the numerator of the right hand side. This may sometimes lead to negative values of a . In such situations, we construct our path as though a were positive and then traverse the path in the direction opposite to the normal convention.

At this point, it is worth noting that as the disk moves along the sides QR and SP of the rectangular path $PQRSP$ in Fig.3, the value of α would have to change in the absence of rolling. This may not be simple to achieve in practice as in the case of a unicyclist. We therefore modify our rectangular path to the path $PQMNP$ in Fig.3 where α would change only when the disk is rolling. It is easy to show that the surface integrals in Eqs.(10) and (11) will have the same value when the closed curve C is the rectangular path $PQRSP$ or the parallelopiped path $PQMNP$.

Figure 3 Both the closed paths PQRSP and PQMNP in the θ - α plane produce the same desired changes in the dependent variables x and y .

Equation (15) has a singularity for

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_f &= \arctan 2(y_f - y_d, x_d - x_f) - n\pi, \\ n &= 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

There are three simple ways to overcome this problem. One would be to move from the initial configuration to a different intermediate configuration *i.e.* to a different set of values x_d and y_d that would not satisfy Eq.(16). This would require us to choose a different trajectory from O to P (see Fig.3). The second alternative would be to set an intermediate goal x'_f, y'_f

and first move to this configuration from x_d, y_d using cyclic motion of the independent variables. Then the remaining task would be to plan a second cyclic motion of the independent variables such that the dependent variables would converge to x_f, y_f from their values x'_f, y'_f . The "smart" alternative would be to follow the three step procedure explained below and graphically shown in Fig.4.

1. Change the present configuration variables θ_f and α_f to some other values θ'_f and α'_f using any trajectory OR , such that $\alpha'_f \neq \alpha_f$ at R . Ignore the evolution of the variables x and y that take the new values x'_d, y'_d at R from their values x_d, y_d at O .
2. Construct any closed path C passing through R , that will change the x and y variables by amounts $(x_f - x_d)$ and $(y_f - y_d)$ respectively. If we choose a rectangular path, or the equivalent parallelogram path, then the dimensions of this path would be computed from Eqs.(14) and (15) only by replacing α_f in Eq.(14) by α'_f . Move along this closed trajectory once to come back to R where $\theta = \theta'_f$ and $\alpha = \alpha'_f$.
3. Retrace backwards the trajectory OR to move from R to O . At O the configuration of the system would be $(x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f)$.

Figure 4 A graphical representation of the singularity avoidance scheme.

The above procedure for singularity avoidance follows from our discussion in section 2.2. This procedure is also recommended for avoiding points close to singular points. At points close to the singularity, trajectories tend to become infeasible due to the large magnitude of a , as evident from Eq.(15).

We are now convinced that any configuration of the rolling disk $(x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f)$ can be reached from any initial configuration $(x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i)$ by using the motion planning algorithm discussed in this section. Though in certain situations there may be a singularity problem, this problem can be easily overcome. The singularity that we may encounter is however not a physical singularity, it is rather an algorithmic singularity.

We illustrate our path planning algorithm with the help of a simple example. In this example we come close to the singularity, and we tactfully avoid it using the “smart” algorithm discussed above. Consider a disk of radius $r = 0.25$ m which is at its current configuration $(x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i) \equiv (0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$ meters, degrees. Suppose the desired configuration of this disk $(x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f)$ is $(-0.4, 1.0, 180.0, 22.5)$ meters, degrees. We first converge the variables θ and α to their desired values using the simple straight line path OZ , as shown in Fig.5. The coordinates of x and y at the end of this path will be $x = x_d = 0.1522$ and $y = y_d = 0.7654$ meters respectively (obtained through numerical simulation). Using Eqs.(14) and (15), we solve for a and b to find $a = 132.72$ radians and $b = 0.01808$ radians. Clearly, we are close to a singular configuration. In light of the discussion on singularity avoidance, we adopt the following measure. We have complete liberty to choose θ'_f and α'_f (point R in Fig.4) with the only restriction being that $\alpha'_f \neq \alpha_f$. We choose $(\theta'_f, \alpha'_f) = (\theta_i, \alpha_i) = (0.0, 0.0)$ and we change θ_f and α_f to θ'_f and α'_f by retracing the path OZ backwards (see Fig.5). We therefore come back to the initial configuration where $(x, y, \theta, \alpha) = (x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i)$. Now we substitute the value of α_i in place of α_f in Eq.(14) and solve for a and b from Eqs.(14) and (15). We obtain $b = 0.8034$ radians or 46.03 degrees and $a = 3.068$ radians or 175.78 degrees. In Fig.5, the path $OPQRO$ is the closed path constructed with these values of a and b . The path is chosen to be a parallelogram instead of a rectangle for reasons discussed earlier in this section. Due to the motion along this closed path the change in the x and y coordinates will be $(x_f - x_d) = (-0.4 - 0.1522) = -0.5522$ meter and $(y_f - y_d) = (1.0 - 0.7654) = 0.2346$ meter respectively. Therefore the coordinates at O of the dependent variables after the motion along the closed path will be $x = -0.5522$ and $y = 0.2346$ meters. Finally, we trace the straight line path from O to Z . Due to this motion, the change in the x and y coordinates will be $(x_d - x_i) = (0.1522 - 0.0) = 0.1522$ meter and $(y_d - y_i) = (0.7654 - 0.0) = 0.7654$ meter respectively. Therefore, the coordinates at Z will be $x = x_f = (-0.5522 + 0.1522) = -0.4$ meter and $y = y_f = (0.2346 + 0.7654) = 1.0$ meter. The coordinates of the independent variables at Z are obviously $\theta = \theta_f = 180.0$ degrees and $\alpha = \alpha_f = 22.5$ degrees. Looking back at the entire motion, we realize that the initial path from O to Z and back to O was redundant. Therefore, a path that would be sufficient for converging all the variables is $OPQROZ$ as shown in Fig.5.

The complete path $OPQROZ$ is quite different

from paths that are generated in the absence of singularity. In the absence of singularity, the complete path consists of an initial path segment followed by a closed loop in the θ - α plane. In the particular example considered, we had a singularity and the complete path consisted of a closed loop path followed by a simple path segment. The simulation results for this particular example are shown in Fig.6. The points $O, P, Q, R,$ and Z in Fig.6 correspond to the same points in Fig.5.

Figure 5 The path $OPQROZ$ is the outcome of the successful implementation of the singularity avoidance scheme for the rolling disk, discussed in section 3.

The singularity problem discussed above arises due to the particular nature of our algorithm where we converge both the dependent variables x and y simultaneously using closed trajectories of the independent variables. We have seen that this is not at all a serious problem. However, this problem can be completely eliminated by adopting a slightly different algorithm. The idea behind this algorithm is to use repeatable motion of one of the dependent variables. This algorithm is discussed next.

In our singularity free algorithm, we will first converge the independent variables θ and α from their initial values (θ_i, α_i) to their desired values (θ_f, α_f) . Let us suppose that the dependent variables x and y change their coordinates from x_i and y_i to x_d and y_d respectively. We will next converge x to its desired value x_f using closed trajectories of the independent variables without being concerned about the evolution of the y coordinate. Specifically, we will use Eq.(12), where we will have the liberty to choose a set of values a and b . Let us suppose that the dependent variable y drifts from its previous coordinate y_d to y'_d in this process. We will finally converge y from its present coordinate y'_d to its desired value y_f using closed trajectories of the independent variables that will also produce a closed trajectory of the dependent variable

x , *i.e.* a repeatable motion in the x coordinate. From Eqs.(12) and (13) it follows that the correct choice of the variables a and b for this repeatable motion should be

$$b = -2\alpha_f \pm (2n + 1)\pi, \quad a = \frac{\Delta y}{2r \cos \alpha_f},$$

$$\alpha_f \neq \pm(2n + 1)\pi/2, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (17)$$

where $\Delta y = (y_f - y'_d)$, and b will be chosen such that $b > 0$. The magnitude of a can however be positive or negative. We will use the absolute value of a to construct the parallelogram path in the θ - α plane. If the sign of a is obtained negative from Eq.(17), then the use of the positive value will bring about a change in the y coordinate by an amount $-\Delta y$ instead of Δy . This problem can be simply solved by changing the direction of travel along the closed path. This idea has been appropriately demonstrated in the next simulation.

Figure 6 Path OPQROZ shows the motion of the disk rolling on the x - y plane for the singularity avoidance scheme discussed in section 3.

As an alternative, we could also converge the dependent variable y before we converge the dependent variable x . In that case, after the initial motion from the configuration $(x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i)$ to the configuration $(x_d, y_d, \theta_f, \alpha_f)$, we would suitably choose a and b in Eq.(13) such that y converges from y_d to y_f . At this stage we will not be concerned about the evolution of the x coordinate, which will drift from x_d to x'_d . Finally, we will change the variable x by an amount $\Delta x = (x_f - x'_d)$ using closed trajectories of θ and α that will also produce a closed trajectory of y , *i.e.* a repeatable motion in the y coordinate. From Eqs.(12) and (13) it then follows that the correct choice of the variables a and b would be

$$b = 2(n\pi - \alpha_f), \quad a = \frac{\Delta x}{2r \sin \alpha_f},$$

$$\alpha_f \neq \pm n\pi, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (18)$$

where, b will be chosen such that it is a positive number, and the absolute value of a will be used to construct the trajectory. The direction of travel along the closed trajectory should be along the positive or the negative direction depending upon whether the sign of a comes out to be positive or negative in Eq.(18).

From the two alternatives we conclude that if the final value of α is such that $\alpha_f = \pm(2n + 1)\pi/2$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, then we will first converge y and then converge x . If $\alpha_f = \pm n\pi$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, then we will first converge x and then converge y . For $\alpha_f \neq n\pi/2$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, either of the two alternatives mentioned above can be adopted.

Figure 7 The path OPQRSXYZP was planned using the singularity free algorithm with a repeatable motion in the x coordinate.

To illustrate the efficacy of this singularity free algorithm, we consider the same example we have considered before. The initial configuration of the disk of radius $r = 0.25$ meters is $(x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i) \equiv (0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$ meters, degrees, and its desired configuration is $(x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f) \equiv (-0.4, 1.0, 180.0, 22.5)$ meters, degrees. We first converge the independent variables using a straight line path (path segment OP in Figs.7 and 8) in the θ - α plane. At the end of this path the configuration of the system is found to be $(x, y, \theta, \alpha) = (0.1522, 0.7654, 180.0, 22.5)$ meters and degrees respectively. Since $\alpha_f = 22.5$ degrees $\neq n\pi/2$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we are free to converge either x or y initially. We choose to converge x first. In Eq.(12), we substitute $x_f = -0.4$ meters, $x_d = 0.1522$ meters, and $\alpha_f = 22.5$ degrees. Choosing $b = 60$ degrees or 1.047 radians, we obtain $a = 3.628$ radians or 207.87 degrees. For these values of a and b , the closed path is given by $PQRSXP$ in Fig.7. After moving along this path, the y variable drifts from $y_d = 0.7654$ meters to $y'_d = 1.485$ meters, as shown in Fig.8, whereas

the x coordinate converges to its desired value. Now the task is to generate a closed path in the θ - α plane that will cause a repeatable motion in x but will converge y to $y_f = 1.0$ meter. Using Eq.(17) we arrive at $b = 135$ degrees or 2.356 radians and $a = -1.05$ radians or -60.15 degrees. For these particular values of a and b , the closed trajectory is given by $PXYZP$ in Fig.7. Due to the negative value of a , the direction of this closed path is opposite to our usual convention. The entire motion of the system can be obtained by eliminating the redundant path segment SPS . Therefore the complete motion of the system would be $OPQRSXYZP$, as shown in both Figs.7 and 8.

Figure 8 Path $OPQRSXYZP$ shows the motion of the disk rolling on the x - y plane for the singularity avoidance scheme with a repeatable motion in the x coordinate.

4 Conclusion

A motion planning algorithm for nonholonomic mechanical systems was presented in this paper. In this algorithm, the independent variables of the system were first converged to their desired values. Subsequently, the dependent variables were converged using closed trajectories of the independent variables. The

motion planning algorithm was found to have certain global attributes which answered questions pertaining to the reachability of the system. The algorithm also allowed for motion planning in the presence of additional constraints. The salient features of the algorithm were aptly illustrated through the example of a disk rolling without slipping on a flat surface.

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